

A Different Assessment: "From Small to Large" and "From Nothing to Existing"

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I wrote this article being inspired by the information in the books which I mentioned in the references.

Abstract

If a beginning point is unavoidable for everything that exists, a different approach can be presented at the zero-point. From the smallest particle to the largest object, and from the lowest energy level to the highest energies, this difference entails going beyond the configurations and processes that arise in various related embodiments. If something can exist from nothing, so can that thing disappear. The existence of zero-point has to be determined with the least amount of mistakes, only then the path to disappearance becomes clear.

The term vacuum means the temporary or permanent disappearance of matter and energy and the return to zero in the fields forming the space which is filled by matter and energy. Zero points are the fields with potential.

This potential is in a state of equilibrium with the potential of matter and energy. This can be likened to the energy (x) time uncertainty, but there is the effect of vacuum instead of time here. This equilibrium or disequilibrium is the main characteristic on which the model is based. The process beginning from the zero-point creates two structures opposed to each other that can be damping each other like the same waves. Positive energy and negative energy. These energies, not only opposed to each other but also interconnected, became the raw material of the particles. As the enormous vacuum field filled with enormous positive and enormous negative energy, how come did such tiny particles form and our universe come into existence? This transformation depends on the behavioural characteristics of negative and positive energies. Types of particles are formed when these energies gathered in different combinations. However, positive and negative energy did not only form the particles but also made the particles move.

Due to the vacuum (x) energy equilibrium I mentioned above, the particles again faced disappearance. Thus, the vacuum (x) energy equilibrium turned into an existence-disappearance equilibrium. This led to the emergence of all forces.

Keywords: Response to vacuum, Negative energy, Positive energy, Beginning, Equilibrium of matter, Potential of nothingness, Balance.

1. Introduction

The model that I will try to explain aims at combining and integrating classical physics and modern physics.

To specify the effective variables in determining the situation, it is necessary to select the zero point as the beginning as accurately as possible. The more accurate the zero point is selected, the faster

and more continuous the progress will be. We can create a projection from the Big Bang to the present. But when we determine the situation, the variables are not sufficient. Therefore we have to make a different selection at zero-point. The more inclusive this selection is, the easier it will be for the variables to fall into place, zero-point is going begin with equilibrium or disequilibrium.

If something can come out of nothing, it can disappear, and it can return to its beginning. In fact, everything that exists has the potential to create the one which created itself. This may or may not be a repetitive process, but when we understand any existence-disappearance, we understand everything. If we have a complete sample as a whole, we can have the possible knowledge of everything. The model I will explain is based on the logic I have pointed out above.

Primarily, we need to focus on four structures.

I. Black holes: Although there are different views on the assumption that black holes emit radiation, the view that radiation originates from the interaction between the black hole and the vacuum around it is a very consistent approach, and it is very close to the truth. As the amount of mass forming the black hole increases, the vacuum formed around it will be much more effective and more extensive.

Theoretically, the most advanced level of this is the vacuum field created by the collapse of a universe on itself. This causes such an influential vacuum effect that the first seeds of a new universe can flourish at the borders of the collapsing universe, just as the black hole creates radiation.

II. Particle-antiparticle: The behaviours and effects of the particle and antiparticle are guiding. It is a very special case that everything about them is the same, just like the copy of each other, even the absolute value of their electromagnetic charges is the same, they lose their mass as a result of contact through interacting with each other, and all of them turn into bosons or in other words into energy. Fermions produce bosons both inside and outside the nucleus, but they do not lose all of their mass in this way. Therefore it is necessary to understand this special state of the particle and antiparticle by analyzing the internal mechanism of the charge and the matter better.

III. Wave-particle duality: In a wave-particle duality, how is it possible that the interference pattern and the possibility of where the particle can be found give the same results? How come do the possibilities match the interference pattern exactly? In this case, the field where the motion of the particle takes place acts as if there is a wave motion. If this field is composed of two different, opposite characteristics and repetitive parts and surrounds the particle, if it is in periodic or similar motion, the particle may proceed in a wave-like manner. In such a case, the motion must be defined differently.

IV. Wave dynamics: In physics, the only formation that removes each other along with the effects without transforming into any other form is waves, but by means of an equation that gives negative analysis, theoretically we can mention negative energy as well as positive energy, and according to classical physics, negative energy and positive energy can damping each other like the waves.

2. Any Beginning

2.1. The First Phase: Response to Vacuum, Initial Motion

The place where the universe started should be a huge vacuum field or a huge nothingness field. How this field has emerged has secondary importance. What really matters is what came into existence in this field. This may be the edge of a collapsing universe or the first vacuum field, which is the beginning of everything. Since the beginning arose from nothingness, the first and most significant conservation, such as energy conservation, should be the conservation of the vacuum field and its effect and followed by the conservation of the value of the universe field. Therefore there should be a relationship like the principle of uncertainty in the form of “the value of the vacuum field (x) the value of the universe field.” In other words, everything and nothing that exists together, create a balance. Thus, the emerging universe, from its smallest elements to the largest, exists and disappears continually.

In the model, which I will describe, what I mean by vacuum is the space that reacts to nothingness almost instantaneously. When I express nothingness, I mean the disappearance of the structures that I will describe, that is to say, in the field covered by these structures. Otherwise, empty space becomes completely meaningless. The effect of this vacuum is directly proportional to the density of the constituent structures of existence.

For the reasons I mentioned in four structures that I wrote above, it is necessary to define matter and motion differently.

In Particle Physics and Astrophysics, in the world of the smallest and the largest, we observe that there is a constant state of motion. What is the source of the motion? Theoretically, quantum mechanical calculations have shown that if the negative and the positive mass are together, they cause a motion continually. If the negative energy field and the positive energy field are together, then the same motion is effective. Furthermore, according to classical physics, the negative energy field and the positive energy field annihilate each other by interacting together.

After understanding the mechanism of blackbody radiation, we know that energy can exist in packets. Therefore, all forms of energy, whether positive or negative, will exist in packets. In my opinion, the classical physics approach and quantum mechanical calculations do not differ. When the energy packets are equal, in other words, when the absolute values of the positive energy field and the negative energy field are equal, they are damped like waves if they are in full contact with each other. But when they are not equal, they cause motion due to their effects on each other.

In the model which I will describe, the first steps of motion originate from the effects of energy fields on one another. In the fields of vacuum, both positive and negative energy fields are formed just like the formation and the disappearance of particles. They may have strong or weak effects depending on the fields in which they are formed. While a virtual positive energy field and a virtual negative energy field can be formed in a weak vacuum field, an actual positive energy field and an actual negative energy field can be formed in a much more effective vacuum field. But when these energy levels are formed, whether virtual or actual, they do not need to borrow energy as in the virtual particles because

the positive energy field and the negative energy field together generate a zero-energy state. I think that's how it all started.

Our universe may have started in the vacuum field of any universe which was not dark energy dominated and had been collapsed. Because the galaxies are pulled aside, I believe everything started in the vacuum field, which was formed from the boundaries of a collapsing universe.

2.2. The Second Phase: Expansion, Existence of Only Very Small Ones

I think that in a very effective vacuum field, both positive energy field and negative energy field emerged adjacently from a single point and with a power which is equal to the effect of this vacuum. Regarding the nature of these fields, I can say that the positive energy field appears to a large extent in the forces that are effective in a gathering of small and large formations in our universe. In other words, the positive energy field has the characteristic of gathering. The negative energy field should also contain the opposite characteristics. In other words, the characteristic of expanding its field and dispersing. However, there is another feature of the fields having these two opposite properties. The affinities of the fields to each other, it is a kind of pulling force. This feature is common and completely identical.

I asked myself that question. Henceforward what kind of a course do these fields which emerged adjacently follow? They would try to protect their contact surfaces due to their affinity to each other. However, their characteristics are so opposing that, since one of them has the gathering characteristic and the other one has the dispersing characteristic, they will not be able to reach each other completely, the equivalent of their power on contact surfaces would not remain the same. Therefore they would not be able to annihilate each other. In physics, there are many non-interacting conditions as their energy levels are not equal. These fields are in the same position. This position has led to the existence of both fields. Later, while the negative energy field tries to expand its volume within a very fast process, the positive energy field that comes into contact with the negative energy field would try to surround the negative energy in the widest possible field due to pulling force. In this case, I would like to draw attention to three effective forces. 1- A sort of pulling force existing between two fields through holding the contact surfaces to the greatest extent possible. 2-The tendency of reducing the gathering volume of the positive energy field. 3- Tendency of increasing the dispersing volume of the negative energy field (since these energies and their characteristics appear as the result of the vacuum effect, I do not specify vacuum as a force separately). These three forces try to form their integrities both acting like a forming balloon membrane and also like the air that fills the balloon simultaneously. But the vacuum has spread over such a wide area that the fields are not strong enough to fill this place and to form integrity. They disintegrated into very tiny pieces enough to achieve integrity, or the disintegrated pieces may have gone through the process again with the same effect until the formation of negative energy fields that are surrounded with positive energy fields in the form of very tiny pieces.

There may also have been released positive energy fields and released negative energy fields. But what I want to describe is the particles that have formed their integrity.

2.3. Particles

Since the particles formed were very, very tiny, in a way that they are not going to disperse again, they achieved forming integrity by circumferential compressing all around through positive energy and pushing centrally through negative energy. However, their existence was only possible if the positive parts and negative parts were not equal. Therefore, particles with negative excess and particles with positive excess were able to exist. Those with equal fields annihilated each other.

By considering the behavioural characteristics of positive and negative energy, it can be seen that this structuring has similarities with wormholes. Although they have similarities in terms of forces, their effects on space-time are different. But their geometries can match, and some of their behaviours may be similar. Besides, the positive energy I have mentioned in this model has similar characteristics to the positive energy of today's physics, but there are some different aspects. For example, as I mentioned above, it is an important part of the mass and particles. However, it's not entire but just the shell.

As the particles filled the vacuum zone, the vacuum had lost its initial effect but was still quite effective. The resulting particles had the ability to do what was necessary to counteract this effect. While the particles were forming, they could not fill the vacuum zone in such a way as to leave no gaps, but they affected vacuum because they continued to exist in integrity. All particles, both with negative and positive excess, were surrounded with energy fields all around, according to their excess, there was energy balancing in the vacuum zone where they were surrounded. Due to the very small excesses, the energy balancing in the current vacuum started very weakly, some kind of virtual fields were formed. The positive virtual fields around those with negative excesses, and negative virtual fields around those with positive excesses. Thus, the surface in contact with the vacuum became surrounded by a positive virtual area in one particle and a negative virtual area in the other particle. The vacuum created an effect that would form negative and positive fields as balanced. The positive virtual field around the negative virtual field and the negative virtual field around the positive virtual field were formed as the secondary. These virtual processes continued in the form of 3,4,5... layers until they filled the entire vacuum. Fermions are those with negative excess; bosons are those with positive excess. Both types of particles formed a negative nucleate structure surrounded by a positive shell. While bosons form a single piece continuous positive shell, negative excess of fermions overflows from a shell, That is to say, the positive shell of the fermions is also one piece but not continuous. The geometries of these structures have important effects.

3. Balance of Everything with Nothing

All kinds of existence models emerge with conservation characteristics. There will be a few different conservation characteristics in this model, as well. This is inevitable. The virtual layers formed around the particles continued, in the form of first positive, second negative, third positive... in fermions, and continued, in the form of first negative, second positive, third negative... in bosons. Under these circumstances, what happened in the vacuum should be as follows. The wider and more effective the vacuum field, the shorter the response time. That is to say, the occurrence of positive-negative fields will be so fast. Otherwise, it means a longer response time. Since the area covered by the particles is small, the vacuum field will be small and weakly effective and, the response time will be long. As molecules are formed and the mass of the objects increases, the response will be shorter as the vacuum will be wider and more effective. In a vacuum, whether it is the virtual energy field or the actual energy field, the positive and negative emerge simultaneously or close to it. After the particles existed, this synchronicity shifted slightly. Nevertheless, everything occurs at speed far beyond imaginable. The moment at which the particles are formed, while the first layer of virtual layers is formed, the second layer starts and then, while the second layer is formed, the third layer starts and so on. Because the field of vacuum shrinks at each stage and its effect is also reduced, the layers become weaker more and more. At one moment of this chain reaction that takes place with incredible speed, the field in the first layer, which is the most powerful layer of the virtual field, reaches the level to neutralize the excess part of the particle, and the particle disappears.

Neutralization spreads over the entire virtual field as a chain reaction. Neutralization always starts from the first layer because the initial balanced energy is here. While the particle disappears together with the first layer, since the particle is found at a point that disappears first, the vacuum becomes most effective at this point until the process is completed and then spreads all around. However, the empty space is filled with virtual particles in an instant. This situation is a process that is similar to the start I mentioned above. However, the vacuum here is very, very small and weak. Therefore, virtual particles dominate, and a very very small virtual model of the start is formed. Virtual particles circulate, such as indistinct drafts. Then as one of these virtual particles rapidly transforms into a real particle at or near the starting point of disappearance in the remaining area. In the remaining regions, virtual energy layers rapidly are formed as 1,2,3...positive-negative-positive... or negative-positive-negative... and virtual particles neutralize. It all returns to the beginning. This repetitive process is the existence and disappearance of our universe continuingly at the particle level.

4. Virtual Geometries, Dynamics of Motion and its Effects

The process which I described above takes place at incredible speeds and time intervals. I can say that these time intervals are similar to the intervals like Planck time. While atoms and molecules are formed, fermions and bosons interact with the fields of existence and disappearance. Keeping in mind these interactions to explain later, I want to tell you now how I see the process in molecules and large objects.

Existence is represented by particles and virtual energy layers, while disappearance is represented by virtual particles. The substances formed by physical-chemical, and mechanical effects are synchronised by interacting with the mutual virtual layers, and atoms, molecules and objects of any size are formed integrated. As atoms and molecules are formed, and the mass of objects increases, the same process applies to large structures.

Each object is surrounded with virtual fields in the form of first layer positive, second layer negative, third layer positive Considering the compression effect of positive energy to a small volume and the expansion effect of negative energy to a large volume, I would say that each of the virtual layers grows like two dimensional due to their effect on each other (small particles formed large particles and objects). While the objects grow in volume, the virtual layers grow in the form of two-dimensional fields. Practically, we can think of objects as three-dimensional and each layer as two-dimensional. As I have already mentioned before, the geometries of these structures have important effects. Because as the objects grow in size, the quantity of negative excesses of the fermions increases in volume, and from the positive virtual field in the first layer, the entire virtual field turns into an indented state to balance. Initially, it is in a wavy state in atoms and small molecules, but as the masses of the objects increase, it turns into sharper indentations and protrusions. Once the masses increase and the indentations and protrusions are formed, while the layers are only parallel to the surface of the objects, they start to become both perpendicular and parallel. In very large masses, it becomes so sharp that the boundaries of the layers become as if they are intertwined. As can be understood from this structure, the number of indentations and protrusions and sharpness of the virtual layers is directly proportional to the mass. And because of this change, the number of indentations and protrusions and sharpness of the layers becomes inversely proportional to the surface area of the objects. The most advanced level of this geometric structure will, of course, occur in celestial objects.

The geometry of the energy fields in objects and particles is very important. Especially the stability of everything depends on the geometries. Changes in how the existence-disappearance works and as the masses of the objects increase and the molecules get bigger are as follows: Existence-disappearance is a very very fast and incredible process, but it consists of two separate phases.

The moment of existence and the moment of disappearance can always be separated at very very short intervals. As I mentioned earlier, the higher the mass, the greater the effect of the vacuum, the shorter the response time, i.e., the beginning of existence- disappearance takes place at shorter intervals. Since the volume the elementary particles occupy in the space is small, their mass is small, and the effect of the vacuum is weak, the existence-disappearance response intervals become long. As the masses increase, the effects of vacuum increase as molecules and objects form and the existence-disappearance response intervals become shorter. The other phase is the completion time of existence and the completion time of disappearance. Completion times extend as molecules grow and masses increase. However, since the interval of starting moments does not extend likewise, disappearance starts before existence is complete, and vice versa, existence begins before disappearance is complete.

They occur as intertwined processes. We can also think of this condition as overlapping processes. We measure an average mass due to this condition which continues regularly. What happens to large masses, as a symbolic analogy is that the sharp image of the object becomes sharp again while it becomes blurred, or it is like a heartbeat. However, they are not processes of traceable length, everything happens in a very short time, but there are temporal differences with respect to small particles. The geometry of atoms and temporal differences of processes have very important effects. An important effect, for example, is the effect on movement. Since existence-disappearance is the general feature in all objects it is not possible for the motion to follow a continuous course; inevitably it becomes intermittent. In addition, the virtual field around the moving object which is evident at high speeds changes. The existence-disappearance response intervals are shortened because the area in front of the motion compresses, the area behind it expands, which strengthens the positive virtual field in the front and the negative virtual field in the back. The negative virtual field in the front can resist compression, so it is not weakened too much and the positive virtual field in the back is not affected much by the expansion and in total both the positive and negative fields gain strength. This strengthening affects both density and geometries. (It is possible, but not necessary, that the density of real part and virtual part change with the change of the geometry, but the change of the density probably changes the geometry). As the disappearance-existence continues, a more effective vacuum is formed and this is reflected in the object as an increase in mass, and all the particles of the object are affected in the form of mass increase. The mass increase due to the motion of the object causes an increase in the positive shell and negative central field in the particles. The negative excess of the fermionic structure also increases. Negative excess of fermions has very important effects. I will try to explain these effects when describing the interactions of particles.

The increase in mass in the particles causes prolongation of the existence-disappearance process (although the initial intervals of existence-disappearance are shortened). The intertwined process causes more existence in time. This the first factor, that causes the time to be perceived slowly. I will try to explain this and the second factor when describing the interaction of particles.

5. Real Geometries, Particle Interactions with All Forces

I have tried to explain why the particles are so small. To be able to exist in this model is only possible in very small sizes. Large structures disperse. I pointed out three forces at the beginning of my paper under the heading "The Second: Phase: Expansion, Existence of Only Very Small Ones". To avoid confusion I have not explained the importance of the geometry of particles, before, which is the fourth effect apart from these three forces. In my paper, from time to time I state that geometries are very important. However, at this stage, I will try to explain why they are so important. Perhaps the geometric structure cannot be considered as a force, but it is critical for the sustainability of existence. The longevity of particles depends on their geometry. The Virtual layers are compatible with these geometries. However, some conditions affect the geometry of the virtual layers. This effect is reflected

in the particles and differentiation occurs in their environment. Existence-disappearance has a very delicate balance. The existence of the particle depends on the compatible existence and disappearance. Otherwise, either the particle cannot exist or it becomes short-lived and transforms into another form. Whether existence-disappearance continues conformably depends on geometry. I describe the geometries in, two separate headings which are virtual geometries and real geometries. Both of these are effective in quarks, electrons, photons, that is, in all known fermion groups, bosons and also hadron groups play a key role in strong nucleus force, weak nucleus force, the electromagnetic force, and gravity. The balanced and apparent effects of these forces depend on the fact that the geometries form a durable structure. Because any effect that can disrupt geometries will transform the particles into an unstable form, and prevent, the existence-disappearance to be continuous. Geometric forms change as they transform, from basic particles into multiple structures. The existence-disappearance of multiple structures occurs in increasing vacuum fields and their geometry varies greatly concerning the basic particles. If the processes of existence-disappearance were not prolonged and if there were no intertwined or overlapping processes and if there were moments that we could call nothingness, as in the basic particles, existence-disappearance could not have continued again and again due to changing geometries. As objects grow, they can protect their existence because their existence-disappearance is not like basic particles. Because if the process did not extend as the masses increased, they would not reappear in the event of near-complete disappearance, and the balance, of existence-disappearance, could not be maintained in large masses and large geometries would have no chance. I think geometry is the reason why many particles appearing in particle colliders are short-lived. Due to the high velocity of the particles in the colliders, their life span appears to be longer. By the way, I think one of the factors in time dilation, which I mentioned earlier that I would write about it, is as follows. The existence and disappearance processes of particles which occur in the collider and gain mass at high speeds are prolonged. As the response times get shorter, closer existence-disappearance occurs. Therefore, the durability of the particle increases (It is similar to what happens when multiple structures and large objects are formed).

Fermions have negative excess and bosons have positive excess.

I think that the exclusion effects of the fermions are due to these negative excess and that the bosons can come together since they are completely covered with a positive shell. I have stated that the source of the speed of the particles is the effect of positive and negative energy on each other. But why are bosons so fast and massless, and why are fermions slower and mass owner? The fact that their fields are different and that these two structures are formed in very different forms reveals this discrepancy. Since the virtual layers of the fermion fields start positively, the predominant effect is the virtual positive energy. In other words, it is the compression effect that reduces volume. This effect acts as a brake while the existence-disappearance continues and keeps the speed within certain limits. It also contributes to the mass. Since the virtual layers of boson fields start as negative energy, the dominant effect is virtual negative energy. In other words, it is a volume increasing and repellent effect. This

effect has very little impact on the particle, that is to say inward, as existence-disappearance continues, It cannot compress the particle. But the outward effect is much more since there are not many barriers against it. It almost opens the path of the particle and causes maximum speed and contributes to the particle to be measured as massless.

As I mentioned before, existence means the dominance of particles and virtual energy layers, and disappearance means the dominance of virtual particles. When objects or particles meet and interact, two separate common fields are formed. The common inner zone in between which is the real field of interaction and the common outer zone surrounding the interacting structures. The combined influence resultant formed by forces in the common inner intermediary field emerges in the common outer field that surrounds. When, the virtual layers of particles or objects contact, they begin to intertwine irregularly. As the existence-disappearance continues, inevitably the equivalent negative layers become neutralized when they become in full contact with the equivalent positive layers. If the vacuum created does not have sufficient opportunity to fill the virtual field again, the objects or particles approach each other and, the diminished virtual field compensated in the common outer zones of the particles or objects approaching each other. This explanation should be viewed as the effects of the existence process, but there is also a phase of virtual particles that are formed in the process of disappearance. Virtual particles fill their fields randomly, just like gas molecules, and affect equal to total momentum. In fermions, the vast majority of virtual particles are in the fermion structure, but virtual bosons can also form due to the conservation of total momentum and energy. These fast virtual fermions create a repulsive effect in particles or objects approaching each other because there the virtual fermion structure creates an exclusion effect and has sufficient power with the contribution of their speed. Existence-disappearance response intervals of in neutral particles or in objects (i.e. from existence to disappearance and from disappearance to existence) are completely equal. As a process, disappearance is equal to the process of existence. Which brings the push and pull closer to being equal to each other as power, but the pulling outweighs a little, and I think this is the source of gravity.

In charged particles or objects, existence-disappearance, response intervals (that is to say, from existence to disappearance and from disappearance to existence) are not equal. The disappearance as a process is not equal to the process of existence. A negative charge occurs when the existence lasts longer and, a positive charge occurs when the disappearance lasts longer. When two negatively charged particles or objects approach each other, as the existence-disappearance is not regular in the virtual layer part, it is very difficult for the positive and negative layer to neutralize and to be attracted to one another by vacuum as a result. Regardless of the forces, for two particles or objects contact and approach each other, the energies of the positive and negative parts of the layers reduce and increase during, the processes of existence-disappearance. The positive layer of two separate particles or objects should meet the negative layer and neutralize, and a sufficient vacuum should be formed. However, the layers of two negatively charged particles or objects, cause them to maintain their

energy at a certain level, as the existence takes longer as a process. Therefore, the fields are not very intertwined and they undergo little neutralization (in neutral cases the energy levels are not mutually constant and overlapping is possible when their existence-disappearance times are equal). The fact that the layers remain more constant process protects their field and makes them stay away from each other strongly. When two positive particles or objects approach each other, virtual particles dominate as a process, and they also stay away from each other strongly, because most of the virtual particles, perhaps all of them, are in the fermion structure. Very little neutralization occurs. When the speed of the virtual particles is taken into account, the dominance of the repulsive effect emerges.

When a positive particle or object and a negative particle or object approach each other, neutralization is possible in the intersecting zone since the existence of one is prolonged, the disappearance of other is prolonged, and they create common fields that make the intermediate vacuum very effective. The vacuum field which is formed by the positive particle that disappears rapidly is occupied by the negative particles and layers approaching it synchronously in a balanced manner, positive and negative particles and layers are attracted to each other up to an appropriate potential. (I will try to describe why gigantic empty spaces occur in atoms later on while explaining how the dynamics of the model will present an approach). While virtual layers form a common field, the virtual particles in the intermediary field form at a very minimal level. But the balance of the vacuum must be maintained. Therefore, the virtual particles are compensated evenly in the common outer fields instead of the field among the opposite electromagnetically charged particles, and if their charge is equal, their outer fields become neutral. (Regardless of attraction and repulsion force, the diminished energy field is compensated in an appropriate field of interaction). Quarks are different from other fermions. Negative residual energies of fermions form as symmetric structure. A symbolic example regarding its form can be as follows. Negative residual effects may be seen evenly at both ends of on symmetrical geometric structure. Thus the negative residual effect shows a symmetrical distribution. But there is no symmetrical distribution of the negative residual effect in quarks. Therefore their interactions as fermions are different. In my opinion, the up quark and the down quark do not have a complex structure. Because otherwise, they would not be able to form protons and neutrons. As a symbolic example regarding the shape of quarks, the negative residual effect may be seen only at one end of the quark structure. That is to say; it has no symmetrical effects. And as such, there may be parts where the negative energy is not effective. Using these parts, which are the dominant effect of purely positive energy, quarks can come side by side very tightly. In protons, two up quarks and one down quark come together side by side to form a perfectly symmetrical structure. In this structure, I think both the residual negative energy parts and the parts with positive energy dominance form a completely symmetrical structure. Almost a structure like a single symmetrical fermion is formed in every aspect. This structure creates quite an extraordinary effect. The quarks are so intertwined that the layers formed at the phases, of existence-disappearance, cannot do not occur separately and they are completely neutralized up to a distance that the layers of all three quarks can reach. And the entire area

of the three is reconstructed in like the first formation of the universe. The virtual layers, which disappear in a large area, create a very effective vacuum effect, and the proton forms an extraordinary layer structure around it like a very big fermion. Due to the extraordinary symmetrical structure of the unified quarks, the construction of the layers takes much longer. Their masses are measured very high since their existence-disappearance processes last long. Furthermore, these layers become dense that they can not even be compared with those of, quarks layers. Again, of first layer positive, second layer negative, third layer positive... continues in the form and as they move away from the proton their effects weaken. In particular, however, the first positive layer is formed much denser than the virtual layers of normal fermions and it creates an effect, in the particle colliders as if the hadrons are soft. The reason why the proton is very durable is that it has a perfectly symmetrical geometry compatible with existence-disappearance. But in neutrons, two down quarks and one up quark cannot form the same durable structure. However, in the nucleus environment, protons come side by side with the neutrons and thus affect each other's geometries and they become more durable. There is no doubt that there are many, interactions and all forces play a role in the nucleus environment, where the four fundamental forces are largely effective. But I think that the symmetrical geometries created by the up and down quarks are the fundamental effect of the nucleus environment. Durable fundamental particles are long-lasting because their geometry is very special. It is highly probable that everything that disrupts geometry will form a flimsy structure. In my opinion, quarks alone cannot last long due to their non-symmetric geometry.

Our universe exists because the very special cases of the up quark and the down quark create a symmetrical geometry together which is a great chance. Except for this exception, I think that quarks are less likely to be durable, when they come together, because in this type of structuring a new geometry is created from scratch, and in the vacuum, the virtual layers are created from scratch. An effect similar to the virtual layers being formed from zero is also observed in the collision of particles at very high speeds. Because at high speeds during existence-disappearance, the virtual layer structure changes quite a lot because of the mechanism which I pointed out earlier. The new particles that are formed in the environments of these two similar conditions have both high mass and become unstable due to their geometry. The common characteristics of these fields formed by different geometries and different structures are more dense layers and constructions which are formed more compact. As in the atomic nucleus, in these fields, the geometry of the particles, especially those that occur close to the, first virtual layer, is not expected to be durable. It does not matter whether the emerging particles are fermionic or bosonic, they are large mass and short-lived. I had stated the reason that the bosons are measured as zero mass is that as of layers the first negative, the second positive and the third negative...continues in the form. However, it can not form their structures in these extraordinary fields. In addition to being short-lived under the effect of these dense layers, their velocities get slower and they are measured as massively. This is what happens in W and z bosons as well.

6. Finally, How Can the Dynamics of This Model Provide an Approach?

In short, I want to take a look at five different situations.

I. We can say that the lower the temperature of the objects, the more stable they are. The prediction of this model is also in this direction. Because as the temperature of the objects increases, the geometric structure of the particles becomes more unstable. Existence-disappearance, of atoms and particles whose kinetic motions increase begin to occur in larger volumes. This situation forces the virtual layers to spread out on larger fields. An effect similar to the mechanism that causes the mass increase on the accelerating particles occurs. And as virtual and real in total, positive and negative energy increases with the change of geometry. Furthermore, as I mentioned below, negative energy leakage may also be occurring at high temperatures which I believe to occur in stars mostly. These changes cause all the energy levels of the atoms to change and radiation, get rid of excess energy and occurs to stabilize.

II. Today's physics has been very successful in explaining the dynamics that happen in the stars and prevailing there but the dynamics of this model can provide a different approach. Occur very large kinetic energies in stars nuclear reactions, particle collisions, the formation of new particles, the decomposition of many particles, the formation, and decomposition of atoms, the formation, and decomposition, of molecules. This situation, although it can be explained in terms of the observed results, there should be additional explanations of the processes in terms of the internal structure of the unobservable matter. According to this model, the collisions created by the complex environment occur in these processes, while in the existence-disappearance phases, due to the dispersion and expansion, of negative energy some of it leaks out of stars. The positive energy must be decreased to compensate for the lost negative energy. This takes place only by releasing photons because they have residual positive energies, but it is not possible to compensate for the lost negative energy continuously, so the positive energy increases continuously in the total. I think that this situation has an important effect, on the cooling and loss of energy of the star along with other processes. I also think that an increase in positive energy, the compression and gathering characteristics of positive energy play an important role in the formation of black holes. Almost all matter is transformed into a bosonic structure.

III. The particles come together with their antiparticle and completely transformed into photons. This situation is similar to the mechanism in the stars.

What kind of approach can this model provide for the antiparticles before moving to the antiparticle interaction with the particle which is a very interesting form of interaction? I want to mention that. As the mass of anti-particles is the same as the particles and their absolute charge is equal to each other, the explanation that "they are formed together" or "they appear in some particular cases" is not sufficient. This model may provide an additional approach. "One of the particles acting like mould, and they are formed from each other according to that mould" the opinion seems is possible to me as an additional approach. At the beginning of everything, first particles then virtual layers occurred. In

other words, first, actual energy fields and then virtual energy fields occurred. After this process was completed, first, the particle and the then order of the virtual layer is intertwined due to varying environment. Regarding the particles and virtual layers formed by collisions and different effects, because the environment is different, virtual energies could be formed from real energies while real energies could be formed with the effect of virtual energies. In other words, virtual layers and virtual particles can be said to have formed real particles and existence-disappearance configurations were diversified. A good example of this diversification is through electron. The process of existence-disappearance can be interrupted by an effect coming from outside the electron's field and by a powerful virtual layer effect and it can be neutralized and disappear at a moment where the electron should exist. Because it disappears at the time it should have existed, the process may reverse in the empty space that it leaves behind. The vacuum generated in the remaining space may cause the formation of an electron of equal mass with the effect of the virtual layers of the electron. However, it can create an electron with a short existence time and a long disappearance time. This is a positively charged electron. Therefore positron occurs in unstable and complex environments.

When the electron and positron enter each other's electromagnetic field, very quickly they are drawn towards each other, and due to their spins, momentum, and existence-disappearance phases, they cannot advance along a straight line when approaching each other. They approach within the bounds of possibility. Since both the particles and the virtual layers are very balanced with each other, they begin to spin, around each other, very rapidly as they get closer. This causes a part of the negative energy field to leak out of the interaction field, similar to the situation in stars. This causes the positive energy field to be strengthened and the particles to approach each other very strongly. In so much that, they collide strongly, and transform into boson because of the positive excess. This process takes place when the particles have equal mass and balanced layers. Otherwise, the oppositely charged particles do not gain so much speed and not collide. They revolve around each other and remain in balance as in atoms. The interactions of charged particles are strictly dependent on their geometry, temporal differences, and in particular their size, as well as the energy levels and geometries of their virtual layers. In the case of masses alone, the fact that the mass of the proton is much larger than the mass of the electron causes the onset of its virtual layers to possess much higher energy. However, because of the shortness of the effect range and the difference of the completion phase of the process depending on the high mass, that is, as the existence-disappearance processes become more intertwine and the electron-existence-disappearance processes find sufficient time, the positive charge and the negative charge are balanced. Due to the higher potential of the virtual layers of the proton, the electron is only stabilized in a zone appropriate to its potential and cannot be too close to the proton.

That the same reason, the atoms have empty spaces in their structure also that the electron and positron approach each other so strongly.

IV. In single-slit or double-slit interference experiments, processes conducted with electrons create interference patterns through the effects of virtual layers. The electron gets through a single slit.

Because the virtual layers spread over a large area, they infiltrate both slits. However, integrity is impaired. Normally, the electron layers tend to merge because of their positive weight. But in this case, they become dispersed and also asynchronous, because they proceed as low-energy layers without electrons on the one hand and low-energy layers with electrons on the other. But the interaction between the two fields starts immediately. Neutralization zones occur in different parts. This affects the position, of the electron's, existence-disappearance phases. The neutralization zones act as vacuum foci on the existence-disappearance phases. Due to separate asynchronous fields and spin characteristic, the vacuum foci occur which disperse towards both sides and effective in phases existence-disappearance. However, the most effective vacuum foci are formed in the central region. The electron is affected by these vacuum focuses. As if circulating, in these fields it undergoes existence-disappearance phases and reaches the interference pattern field. (Because the energy is divided, the energy of each field is less than normal. Since they are asynchronous, one side always reaches the vacuum level that could create an electron before. The electron emerges wherever appropriate). Due to the low energy, the existence-disappearance response time extends and the process of existence-disappearance, of the electron, gets shorter. In single slit interference experiments, the energy level is normal. Since the layers are not dispersed, vacuum fields are formed close to each other. Overdispersion does not occur and the pattern field is reached in stacks. Even if electrons are sent at very close intervals instead of being sent separately, their normal levels of energy prevent dispersion and because each electron moves in balance with the layers, common neutralization fields are formed only near the central zone. These fields also affect the existence-disappearance phases, as a vacuum focus, but no dispersion is observed.

Due to the negative weight of the boson layers, as I mentioned before, the layers of two separate bosons spread out over a wide area as dispersed and in the event of compression, neutralization fields occur by means of interaction. These fields also affect the existence-disappearance phases, as a vacuum focus. Photons are affected by these focal points and move on to undergoing existence-disappearance phases to form an interference pattern. Therefore it is possible to form an interference pattern with photons in a single range.

V. Since smaller the masses of particles or objects, the longer their interval between existence-disappearance and the longer their response time. The disappearance process is short and complete for fundamental particles; in the next existence, all possibilities become valid. While it can exist in an up-spin state, there is a possibility that it may exist in a down-spin state in the next existence. With a form of existence-disappearance, the geometries of ongoing structures have very important effects and these geometries form very delicate balances, while the electron is moving in a sufficient vacuum field, the possibility of up-spin or down-spin is valid. Nevertheless, for example, trying to determine the spin of the electron in such a manner that will affect the vacuum especially affects the geometry of the virtual layers. This situation does not affect the response intervals in existence-disappearance, but slows the existence-disappearance process, because the changing virtual layer geometry causes the neutralization

to slow down. The prolonged process prevents an adequate, free time interval in the vacuum. In this case, there is no opportunity to freely form the spin state with the layers of the electron, and the spin state remains constant as up or down for a certain time. The spin state freely can occur when conditions change.

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